

(Exact Match)

INDIAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH

Publisher: ASSOC PHARMACEUTICAL TEACHERS INDIA, AL-AMEEN COLL PHARMACY, OPP LALBACH MAIN GATE, HOSUR MAIN RD, BANGALORE, INDIA, 560 027
ISSN / eISSN: 0019-5464
Categories: PHARMACOLOGY & PHARMACY | EDUCATION, SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINES | PHARMACOLOGY & TOXICOLOGY
Web of Science Core Collection: Science Citation Index Expanded
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Formulation and Evaluation of Indomethacin Ophthalmic Inserts

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ABSTRACT

Indomethacin, a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug, has a pronounced analgesic antipyretic and anti-inflammatory action. The prostaglandin inhibitory action of indomethacin has been shown to be useful in relief of pain, muscular edema and other ocular inflammatory condition. An attempt has been made to formulate indomethacin ophthalmic inserts using hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, methyl cellulose and gelatin as polymers by solvent casting method with aim of increasing the contact time, achieving controlled release, reduction in frequency of administration, improving patient compliance and greater therapeutic efficacy. The prepared ophthalmic inserts were then evaluated for uniformity of thickness, weight and drug content and swelling index. In vitro drug release studies of formulated ocuserts were performed by studying the diffusion through artificial membrane (prehydrated cellophane). IR spectral studies were performed to confirm the interaction of drug in formulation using KBr disc method. Out of twelve formulations prepared, the formulation containing HPMC (1.2) showed complete and prolonged release with 97.92% at the end of 7 h. The in vitro release kinetic data was treated according to diffusion model proposed by Higuchi and Peppas in order to assess the mechanism of drug release.

Keywords: Indomethacin, Ophthalmic inserts, HPMC, MC, Gelatin, In vitro release

INTRODUCTION

It is well established that the conventional method of ophthalmic drug administration is instillation of a drug solution or suspension into the cul-de-sac. But this is an extremely inefficient method of dosing, since the bioavailability of the drug from an instilled solution is less than 1% of an administered dose. Moreover, systemic absorption of the drug and additives drained through nasolacrimal duct may result in undesirable effects. An effective way to achieve slow and prolonged absorption in ophthalmic practice is to incorporate a drug into a polymeric film, which when placed in the cul-de-sac of the eye exhibits a prolonged local release for drug action on tissue in the immediate vicinity¹.

Indomethacin, a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (N.S.A.I.D.) has a pronounced analgesic antipyretic and anti-inflammatory action. It is an indole derivative and is very effective in the therapy of rheumatoid arthritis, ankylosing spondylitis and acute gout.

The prostaglandin inhibitory action of indomethacin has been shown to be useful in the relief pain and associated symptoms of primary dysmenorrhea. It is also very effective against patient ductus arterioles.

Indomethacin is available in the conventional ocular drug delivery system as 1% eye drops. It is administered at dosing interval of 1 drop every 4 h for a treatment of muscular oedema and other ocular inflammatory conditions. The eye drops dosage form is convenient to use but most of the drug is diluted by tear and rapidly washed out of the sac by constant tear flow which can be avoided by using insert by which the therapeutic efficiency of ophthalmic drug can greatly improved.²

In the present work an attempt was made to formulate indomethacin ophthalmic inserts using hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, methyl cellulose and gelatin as polymers by solvent casting method with aim of increasing the contact time, achieving controlled release, reduction in frequency of administration, improving patient compliance and greater therapeutic

efficacy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Indomethacin was obtained as gift sample from Bombay tablefs Pvt.Ltd Gandhinagar. Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, methyl cellulose and gelatin were obtained from SD Fine chemicals, Mumbai.

Method for preparation of hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose and methyl cellulose films

The inserts were prepared by solvent casting method. The required quantity of the polymer was weighed and dissolved in distilled water by gentle stirring. The required amount of PEG 400 was added as plasticizer to above solution under stirring condition. The weighed amount of indomethacin (passed through sieve # 400) was added and stirred for 12 h to get uniform dispersion. After complete mixing the casting solution (5 ml) was poured in clean petridish. Then the petridish was dried at room temperature for 24 h. The dried films thus obtained were cut into required size (8 mm diameter) consisting of 2 mg of drug by cork borer and stored till used.³⁻⁵ The formulae for different formulations are shown in the Table-1.

Method for preparation of gelatin films

The required quantity of gelatin and glycerin were weighed and dissolved in water and the mixture was heated at 60°C on a water bath until the entire gelatin was dissolved. The weighed amount of indomethacin (passed through sieve # 400) was added and stirred for 6 h at 40°C on magnetic stirrer to get uniform dispersion. After complete mixing the casting solution (5 ml) was poured in clean petridish. The petridish was cooled at 10°C by placing on ice until the films were gelled. The gelled films were taken out from ice and allowed to dry at room temperature for 24 h. The dried films thus obtained were cut into required size (8 mm diameter) by cork borer and stored till used.^{6, 7} The formulae for different formulations are shown in Table-1.

Evaluation of the prepared formulations⁸⁻¹⁰

Uniformity of thickness

Five films were taken from each batch and their thickness was measured using micrometer screw gauge.

Uniformity of drug content

Five films were taken from each batch and dissolved or crushed in 10 ml of methanol in a beaker and were filtered into the 25 ml volumetric flask and the volume

was made up. One ml of the above solution was withdrawn and the absorbance was measured by UV-VIS spectrophotometer at 318 nm after suitable dilutions.

Swelling index

Three films were weighed and placed separately in beakers containing 4 ml of distilled water. At regular intervals of time (every 5 min), the films were removed and the excess water on their surface was removed using a filter paper and then again weighed. The procedure was continued till there was no increase in the weight. The swelling index was then calculated by dividing the increase in weight by the original weight and was expressed as percentage.

Invitro diffusion studies

The *invitro* diffusion of drug from the dif ophthalmic insert was studied using the classical standard cylindrical tube fabricated in the laboratory. A simple modification of a glass tube of 15 mm internal diameter and 100 mm height. The diffusion cell membrane was tied to one end of open cylinder, which acted as a donor compartment. An ophthalmic insert was placed inside this compartment. The diffusion cell membrane acted as corneal epithelium. The entire surface of the membrane was in contact with the receptor compartment containing 25 ml of phosphate buffer pH 7.4 in 100 ml of beaker. The content of receptor compartment was stirred continuously using a magnetic stirrer and temperature was maintained at 37° ± 0.5°C.

At specific intervals of time, 1 ml of the sample solution was withdrawn from the receptor compartment and replaced with fresh buffer solution. The sample was analyzed for the drug content using UV-VIS spectrophotometer at 318 nm after appropriate dilutions against reference using phosphate buffer pH 7.4 as blank.

Drug excipient compatibility studies

The compatibility between drug and the formulations components were confirmed by infrared spectrophotometer using KBr disc method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Efforts were made to prepare the ocuserts of indomethacin using polymers such as hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, methyl cellulose, and gelatin. The physico-chemical evaluation data presented in Table-2 indicates that the thicknesses of the formulations varied

between $88.00 \pm 1.442 \mu\text{m}$ to 168 ± 0.025 . The result showed that the thickness was uniform. The weight of formulations was ranging from 7.93 ± 0.0005 to 18.78 ± 0.015 mg. The drug content of the formulations were determined according to procedure described in methods. The drug content in all formulations was found to contain 95.80% to 99.15% of indomethacin. The HPMC, MC and gelatin are hydrophilic polymer and are soluble in water. Due to its hydrophilic nature the polymers can be expected to absorb water. So to verify this fact, a swelling index test was carried out.

The result showed that there was no significance variation in the water absorption properties of formulations.

The release profile of the formulation is shown in the Figure 1 to 3. The ophthalmic inserts prepared with HPMC releases the drug completely in 5 to 7 h. The release of the drug from the formulation F1 and F2 were found to be 99.06% and 99.33% at the end of 5 and 6 h respectively. The release of drug from formulation F3 and F4 was found to be 99.30% and 97.92% at the end of 7 h.

Table 1: The formulae of the ingredients used in twelve batches.

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Drug (g)	0.460	0.460	0.460	0.460	0.460	0.460	0.460	0.460	0.460	0.460	0.460	0.460
H.P.M.C. (g)	0.230	0.460	0.690	0.92	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
M.C. (g)	---	---	---	---	0.057	0.115	0.172	0.230	---	---	---	---
Gelatin (g)	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	1.38	1.84	2.30	2.76
PEG 400 (ml) (30%)	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.02	0.05	0.07	0.09	---	---	---	---
Glycerin (ml) (40%)	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.92	1.22	1.53	1.84
Water (ml)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Drug:Polymer ratio	1:0.5	1:1	1:1.5	1:2	1:0.125	1:0.25	1:0.375	1:0.5	1:3	1:4	1:5	1:6

Table 2: Physico-chemical data of ophthalmic inserts

Product Code	Weight in* (mg) $\pm$ SD	Thickness in* (μm) $\pm$ SD	Drug content in* mg $\pm$ SD	% Drug content	Swelling * Index
F1	8.16 ± 0.005	123.33 ± 1.028	1.953 ± 0.012	97.65	1.348
F2	9.75 ± 0.0012	132.66 ± 1.974	1.971 ± 0.005	98.55	1.436
F3	8.00 ± 0.011	136.00 ± 1.210	1.967 ± 0.027	98.35	1.750
F4	8.36 ± 0.010	143.66 ± 1.033	1.971 ± 0.029	98.55	2.153
F5	8.26 ± 0.012	88.00 ± 1.442	1.953 ± 0.007	97.65	1.089
F6	7.93 ± 0.005	90.00 ± 1.156	1.971 ± 0.017	98.55	1.387
F7	9.65 ± 0.001	95.00 ± 1.189	1.934 ± 0.039	96.70	1.554
F8	8.10 ± 0.002	97.00 ± 1.363	1.967 ± 0.015	98.35	1.728
F9	17.13 ± 0.005	100.00 ± 1.225	1.976 ± 0.008	98.80	1.109
F10	18.16 ± 0.030	154.33 ± 1.343	1.953 ± 0.025	97.65	1.655
F11	16.30 ± 0.035	159.00 ± 0.034	1.916 ± 0.010	95.80	2.085
F12	18.78 ± 0.015	168.00 ± 0.025	1.962 ± 0.013	98.10	2.236

*Each reading is an average of three determinations

Table 3: Kinetic data of Drug Release from F1 to F12

Product Codes	First order equation		Higuchi's equation			Peppas double log plots		
	Slope	Rate constant (K) mg. min ⁻¹	Regression coefficient (r)	Slope	Rate constant (K) mg. min ⁻¹	Regression coefficient (r)	Slope	Regression coefficient (r)
F1	-0.004	-0.0092	0.9679	59.351	59.351	0.9793	0.5014	0.9653
F2	-0.0033	-0.0076	0.9717	56.645	56.645	0.9846	0.5361	0.9747
F3	-0.0028	-0.0064	0.9787	52.795	52.795	0.9855	0.5707	0.9815
F4	-0.0023	-0.0053	0.9724	54.117	54.117	0.9898	0.6076	0.9803
F5	-0.0052	-0.0119	0.9937	61.453	61.453	0.9889	0.4591	0.9937
F6	-0.0042	-0.0097	0.9844	59.485	59.485	0.9982	0.5037	0.9984
F7	-0.0034	-0.0078	0.9945	58.329	58.329	0.9945	0.5498	0.9951
F8	0.0030	-0.0069	0.9831	55.288	55.288	0.9923	0.5656	0.9929
F9	-0.0157	-0.036	0.9968	12.228	12.228	0.9929	0.565	0.9902
F10	-0.0126	-0.029	0.9764	10.657	10.657	0.9959	0.5911	0.9902
F11	-0.0101	-0.023	0.9887	10.80	10.80	0.9903	0.6868	0.9889
F12	-0.008	-0.018	0.9813	10.444	10.444	0.9892	0.7361	0.9898

Figure 1: In vitro diffusion of indomethacin from F1, F2, F3 and F4 formulations

Figure 2: In vitro diffusion of indomethacin from F5, F6, F7, F8 formulations

Figure 3: In vitro diffusion of indomethacin from F9, F10, F11, F12 formulations

The formulation with MC showed complete release in 5-6 h. The release of drug from the formulation F5 and F6 were found to be 99.77% and 99.56% at the end of 4

and 5 h respectively. The release of drug from formulation F7 and F8 were found to be 99.07% and 97.88% at the end of 6 h respectively.

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Regression
log plots

... formulation with gelatin as the polymer showed complete release of drug in 0.75 to 2.15 h. The release of drug from formulation F9, F10, F11 and F12 was found to be 99.08, 99.06, 97.71 and 95.54% at the end of 1.15, 1.45, 2 and 2.15 h respectively. It showed that the gelatin could not sustain the release of the drug. The *invitro* release data was also subjected to model fitting analysis to know the mechanism of drug release from the formulations by treating the data according to first order and Peppas equation. The results are shown in Table-3. It indicates that the release of drug from the films might have followed first order kinetics and non-fickian in nature. The Higuchi plot revealed that the release of drug might be diffusion controlled.

CONCLUSION

The formulation of ophthalmic insert containing indomethacin and HPMC (1:2) was promising and *invitro* studies proved the efficacy of preparations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

I express my deep sense of gratitude to M / S. Bombay Tablet Pvt. Ltd., Gandhinagar for providing gift sample of indomethacin.

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